

THE NEXUS BETWEEN UNEMPLOYMENT AND UNEMPLOYABILITY IN THE NIGERIAN LABOUR MARKET

¹Edime YUNUSA

Ph.D. Candidate (Industrial Sociology)

Department of Sociology, Faculty of Social Sciences, Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba, Kogi State-Nigeria.

²Timothy Abayomi ATOYEBI, Ph.D.

Senior Lecturer (Industrial Sociology)

Department of Sociology, Faculty of Social Sciences Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba. Kogi State, Nigeria

³Thomas Imoudu GOMMENT, Ph.D.

Associate Professor (Criminology)

Department of Sociology, Faculty of Social Sciences, Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba, Kogi State, Nigeria

⁴Michael Olumide OWOEYE, Ph.D.

Senior Lecturer (Demography and Social Statistics)

Department of Sociology, Faculty of Social Sciences, Bowen University, Iwo, Osun State, Nigeria

⁵Ukwumonu Patrick OKEME, Ph.D.

Senior Lecturer (Human Resources Management)

Department of Public Administration, Faculty of Management Sciences, Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

The persistent challenge of unemployment in Nigeria, Africa's largest economy, has been a subject of significant concern for policymakers, economists, and social scientists. However, a deeper examination reveals a complex interplay between unemployment and unemployability, two related but distinct phenomena that continue to shape Nigeria's labour market dynamics. This paper therefore, examined the nexus between unemployment and unemployability in Nigeria labour market. The specific objectives of the paper includes to examine the situation of unemployment in Nigeria, identifying the reasons why Nigerian graduates are unemployed and to explore the possible solutions to the problems of unemployability in Nigeria. Using Adaptation of Anomie/Strain Theory, the paper adopted secondary sources of data collection to review relevant materials. The paper revealed that Nigeria's unemployment rate stood at 33.3% in the fourth quarter of 2020, marking a significant increase from 27.1% in the second quarter of the year 2021, and increased to 37.4 percent in the last quater of 2022 and currently increasing from 4.2 to 5 percent in the third quarter of 2023. This translates to approximately 23.3 millions currently unemployed Nigerians. The paper identified major reasons why most Nigerian graduates are unemployed and these include lack of employability skills, lack of emphasis on entrepreneurship in the school curriculum, the quality of training not in sync with the current situation of the society, lecturers not possessing current knowledge, endemic corruption, students' apathetic attitude to education and lack of viable plans after National Youth Service Corp (NYSC) scheme among others. The paper further highlighted strategies to solving unemployability challenges among Nigerian graduates and these include overhauling educational system, organizing marketability and employability skills acquisition programmes, establishing labour market information system, infrastructural development, viable industrial policy formulation among others. The paper concluded that the high rate of unemployment among graduates is not merely as a result of scarcity of job opportunities, but also an upshoot of the inability of many graduates to meet the specific skill requirements of available job positions. It is therefore recommended among others, that there should be an implementation of a nationwide educational reform programme that aligns curricula with industrial needs and integrates practical, digital and soft skills training across all levels of Nigerian educational system.

KEYWORDS: Unemployment, Unemployability, Labour Market, Marketability, Employability Skills, Nigerian Graduates.

INTRODUCTION

It is an undisputable fact that the concepts of unemployment and unemployability in Nigeria are contemporary issues of serious concern. Generally, unemployment refers to a situation where an individual who is willing and able to work is without a job and actively seeking employment. Unemployability, on the other hand, refers to a situation where an individual lacks the necessary skills, education, or experience to be able to find or maintain employment. Unemployment is often a temporary situation that can be resolved with job opportunities, while unemployability requires the individual to improve his or her job-related skills or qualifications to become more relevant in a competitive labour market. Unemployment and unemployability are related but distinct concepts. Unemployment is often the result of factors such as a lack of available job openings, economic downturns, or seasonal work fluctuations. It can also be caused by individual factors such as health issues, personal or family responsibilities, or a lack of transportation (Career Advice, 2023).

The persistent challenge of unemployment in Nigeria, Africa's largest economy, has been a subject of great concern for policymakers, economists and social scientists. However, a deeper examination reveals a complex interplay between unemployment and unemployability, too related but distinct phenomena that continue to shape Nigeria's labour market dynamics. This nexus presents a critical area of study, as it highlights not only the scarcity of job opportunities but also the mismatch between the skills possessed by job seekers and those required by employers.

It is a truism that unemployment in Nigeria has remained steadily high, with recent data from the National Bureau of Statistics (2023) indicating a rate of 33.3% in the fourth quarter of 2022. Unfortunately, this alarming figure fails to capture the full scope of the challenge. The concept of unemployability, which adds another layer of complexity to the issue, refers to the inability of individuals to secure employment due to lack of necessary skills, qualifications, or experience demanded by the job market (Okoye et al., 2021).

The relationship between unemployment and unemployability in Nigeria is multifaceted. On one hand, high unemployment rates can lead to skills atrophy and reduced employability as job seekers spend prolonged periods out of work. On the other hand, the prevalence of unemployability among the workforce contributes to sustained high unemployment rates, creating a self-reinforcing cycle (Adebayo, 2023).

The interconnection between unemployment and unemployability in Nigeria presents a complex and multifaceted challenge that has significant implications for the country's socio-economic development. Unemployment has been a persistent problem in Nigeria for decades. Unfortunately, the concept of unemployability has introduced another dimension to the complexity of Nigerian labour market dynamics (Adebayo, 2023).

Regrettably, Nigeria, being the most populous country in Africa has grappled with high unemployment rates, which stood at 33.3% in the fourth quarter of 2020 (National Bureau of Statistics, 2021). This alarming figure not only represents a vast number of individuals without work but also masks the underlying issue of unemployability that exacerbates the problem. The relationship between unemployment and unemployability in Nigeria is characterized by a cyclical pattern, where one reinforces the other, creating a challenging environment for both job seekers and employers (Okoye et al., 2022).

The Nigerian labour market is marked by a significant skills mismatch, where the competencies possessed by job seekers often do not align with the requirements of available positions. This mismatch is partly attributed to an education system that has been criticized for its inability to produce graduates with practical skills and knowledge demanded by the modern workforce (Adelakun et al., 2023). Consequently, many Nigerian graduates find themselves unemployable, lacking the specific skills required by potential employers.

Furthermore, the rapid technological advancements and changing nature of work globally have created new demands for specialized skills, which many Nigerian job seekers are yet to acquire. This skills gap contributes to a paradoxical situation where unemployment rates remain high despite the existence of unfilled job vacancies in certain sectors (Nwoke et al., 2022).

The nexus between unemployment and unemployability in Nigeria is further complicated by structural issues within the economy, such as an overreliance on the oil sector, inadequate infrastructure, and limited industrialization. These factors have constrained job creation and economic diversification, thereby limiting opportunities for skill development and employment across various sectors (Oloni et al., 2023).

Understanding the intricate relationship between unemployment and unemployability is crucial for developing effective policies and interventions aimed at addressing Nigeria's labour market challenges. This nexus not only affects individual livelihoods but also has serious implications for economic growth and national development. This paper aims at setting the stage for a deeper exploration of the factors contributing to both unemployment and unemployability in Nigeria, their interconnections, and potential strategies to address these challenges. By examining this nexus, we can gain valuable insights into the structural issues affecting Nigeria's labour market and inform more effective policy interventions.

Statement of the Problem

The Nigerian labour market is characterized by a significant skills gap, where the competencies possessed by job seekers often do not align with the requirements of available positions. This mismatch is partly due to an education system that has not kept pace with the rapidly evolving needs of industries, especially in sectors driven by technological advancements. This issue is

compounded by a demographic youth bulge, with a large proportion of the population being young adults entering the job market each year. Many of these young people graduate from educational institutions without the practical skills or work experience that employers seek, making them technically qualified but practically unemployable.

The problem extends beyond fresh graduates to include those who have been out of work for extended periods. Long-term unemployment can lead to skill atrophy, where once-relevant abilities become outdated or diminish over time. This creates a self-perpetuating cycle where the longer an individual remains unemployed, the harder it becomes to secure employment, further entrenching their unemployability. Economic factors also play a crucial role. Nigeria's economy, heavily reliant on the oil sector, has not diversified sufficiently to create a robust job market across various industries. This limited economic diversity restricts the types of jobs available and the skills in demand, further widening the gap between job seekers' qualifications and market requirements.

Additionally, there is a geographical dimension to this issue. Urban areas, particularly major cities like Lagos and Abuja are characterised by concentration of job opportunities, leading to high competition. Meanwhile, rural areas often lack significant formal employment options, creating regional disparities in both unemployment and employability. The informal sector, while providing a livelihood for many, often does not offer the kind of stable, skill-developing employment that enhances long-term employability in the formal job market. This can trap individuals in a cycle of informal, often precarious work that doesn't contribute to their professional development or long-term career prospects.

Addressing this nexus requires a holistic approach that involves reforming the education system to align with industry needs, promoting skills development and vocational training, encouraging entrepreneurship, and implementing policies to stimulate job creation across diverse sectors of the economy. It also calls for bridging the gap between academia and industry to ensure that educational outcomes are more closely tied to labour market demands. The challenge is not just about creating more jobs, but about creating a workforce that is adaptable, skilled, and capable of meeting the evolving needs of employers in a global economy. Solving this intricate problem is crucial for Nigeria's economic growth, social stability, and the realization of its demographic dividend. Arising from the above therefore, this paper examined the nexus between unemployment and unemployability in Nigerian labour market space.

Aim and Objectives of the Paper

The general aim of this paper is to examine the nexus between unemployment and unemployability in Nigeria. Specific objectives of this paper include;

- i. To examine the situation of unemployment in Nigeria

- ii. To identify the reasons why Nigerian graduates are unemployed and unemployable.
- iii. To explore the possible solutions to the problems of unemployability in Nigeria

Methods

As a theoretical one, this paper utilizes secondary sources of data collection from books, journal articles, reports and documented internet sources.

Literature Review

The review of relevant and related literature for this paper was done in line with the aim and objectives of the paper and under the following subheadings:

Conceptual Clarifications

The following key concepts are clarified in the context of this paper:

Unemployment

An unemployed person as defined by the ILO (2024), is a person aged 15 or over who simultaneously meets three conditions: being unemployed for a given week; being available to take a job within two weeks; having actively sought a job in the last four weeks or having found one starting in less than three months.

Unemployability

Unemployability is a situation in which an individual who is ready to work but unable to secure one and is usually a result of a person's own limitations. Some people are unable to work because they are too sick, or they do not have the necessary skills.

Labour Market

There is no universally accepted opinion regarding the use of one of the two phrases; however one has to mention the fact that the use of the term "market" does not mean that labour is behaving like another commodity or service. Meanwhile, a simple definition of the labour market is given by ILO (2014) and which state that labour market is the place where supply and demand meet, working to determine the price and quantity of the work performed. Didier (1997) defines the market as a means of communication through which sellers and buyers will inform each other about what they have, what they need and the prices that they ask or propose, before closing the transaction. This definition has great applicability on the labour market.

In other words, labour market is the market in which the amount of services that correspond to tasks well established in the job description, are offered for a price or remuneration (Boeri, 2013), that is, to exist on the labour market it is necessary for the work be rewarded.

In this context of this paper, labour market is seen as a conceptual space where workers offer their skills and time in exchange for wages, benefits, and other forms of compensation. Employers demand labour and workers supply it. The interaction between these two groups determines wages and employment levels, influenced by factors such as economic conditions, government policies, and social norms.

The Situation of Unemployment in Nigeria

Unemployment remains one of Nigeria's most pressing socio-economic challenges, with far-reaching implications for economic growth, social stability, and national development. The situation has been exacerbated by various factors, including population growth, economic downturns, and the COVID-19 pandemic.

According to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), Nigeria's unemployment rate stood at 33.3% in the fourth quarter of 2020, marking a significant increase from 27.1% in the second quarter of the same year (NBS, 2021). And increased to 37.4 percent in the last quarter of 2022 and currently increasing from 4.2 to 5 percent in the third quarter of 2023. This translates to approximately 23.2 million currently unemployed Nigerians, a figure that underscores the severity of the situation. The youth unemployment rate is particularly alarming, with 42.5% of young people aged 15-34 being unemployed (NBS, 2024).

The COVID-19 pandemic has further aggravated Nigeria's unemployment crisis. A study by Andam et al. (2022) found that the pandemic led to job losses across various sectors, with the informal sector being particularly hard hit. The authors estimated that about 33% of Nigerians experienced job losses due to the pandemic, with many others facing reduced working hours or pay cuts.

Sectoral analysis reveals that unemployment is pervasive across different industries. However, the agricultural sector, which employs a significant portion of the Nigerian workforce, has shown some resilience. Adenuga et al. (2023) noted that while other sectors experienced job losses, agriculture saw a slight increase in employment during the pandemic, highlighting its potential role in addressing unemployment.

Regional disparities in unemployment rates are also evident. The NBS (2021) report shows that unemployment rates are higher in rural areas (34.5%) compared to urban areas (31.3%). Additionally, there are significant variations across states, with Imo State recording the highest unemployment rate of 56.6%, while Osun State had the lowest at 11.7%.

The gender dimension of unemployment in Nigeria is also noteworthy. Oloni et al. (2023) found that women are disproportionately affected by unemployment, with a female unemployment rate of 35.2% compared to 31.8% for males. The authors attribute this disparity to factors such as limited access to education, cultural barriers, and discrimination in the labor market.

Educational level plays a crucial role in employment prospects, but paradoxically, unemployment rates are high even among educated Nigerians. Adelokun et al. (2023) observed that university graduates face significant challenges in securing employment, with many remaining jobless for extended periods after graduation. This phenomenon has been linked to a mismatch between the skills acquired in higher education and the demands of the job market.

The current unemployment situation in Nigeria is further complicated by underemployment, where individuals work fewer hours than they would like or in jobs that do not fully utilize their skills and qualifications. The NBS (2021) reported an underemployment rate of 22.8%, which, when combined with the unemployment rate, indicates that over 56% of Nigeria's labour force is either unemployed or underemployed.

In response to this crisis, the Nigerian government has implemented various initiatives aimed at job creation and skills development. These include the N-Power program, the Youth Enterprise with Innovation in Nigeria (YouWiN) initiative, and the National Social Investment Programme (NSIP). However, Okoye et al. (2022) argued that while these programmes have shown some promise, their impact has been limited due to challenges in implementation, scale and sustainability.

In essence, the current unemployment situation in Nigeria remains critical, characterized by high overall unemployment rates, significant youth unemployment, gender disparities and regional variations. Addressing this challenge requires a multi-faceted approach that encompasses economic diversification, skills development, and targeted interventions to support vulnerable groups and regions.

Factors Responsible for the seemingly High of Unemployment among Nigerian Graduates

The seemingly high rate of unemployment among Nigerian teeming graduates is an issue of great concern necessitated by a lot of factors and among which are highlighted and explained by Aririah (2022) as follows:

Lack of employability Skills: Frankly speaking, most Nigerian graduates are unemployable because they lack employability skills. These skills are the skills that could guarantee employment. So, when graduates lack the relevant skills that are needed in the job market, they may never be able to get employed in any organization. Therefore, it behooves the

Nigerian government to ensure that the education system in the country is improved to a quality standard; else, the same problem will keep moving in circles (Aririah, 2022).

No emphasis is laid on entrepreneurship in the school curriculum: The Nigerian educational system is not organized in a way that it could accommodate entrepreneurship in its curriculum. In short, most students read to just pass their examination and come out with a high CGPA. They are not equipped practically or exposed to the reality of life situations. Therefore, upon graduation, they become confused as to how to handle life and make the best of it, even with good results (Aririah, 2022).

The quality of training is not in sync with the situation of the society: The quality of education offered to students is not tailored to tackle the current need of society. For instance, we are in the innovative era where people make use of their brains more than their hands while working. But it is quite unfortunate that the training in the classroom still focuses on the industrial era. Thus, it could be said that most of the programmes taught in schools are irrelevant to the current world situation (Aririah, 2022).

The criterion of job experience with long years of practice is not favourable: Most recruiters in Nigeria request that applicants must possess some level of work experience with some years of practice. There is no room for fresh graduates to even learn the ropes of the job before perfecting in the job roles. Worse still, most curriculums do not make room for internships where students could learn practical skills before applying for their job roles (Nwoke et al., 2022).

Lecturers do not possess current knowledge: The lecturers in the Nigerian tertiary institutions are supposed to undergo training from time to time to refresh their knowledge in their areas of expertise. But the situation at hand is not so. Their knowledge is obsolete and as such, they can only impact the students based on what they know. Sadly, the skills and knowledge being impacted are not marketable enough to inspire confidence in the students after graduation (Nwoke et al., 2022).

Students are apathetic to education: Education in Nigeria seems to serve as a means to an end. Most students are in school purposely to acquire certificate and start making money as quickly as possible. Many of them are not willing to study to possess the required skills that would enable them earn sufficient money in the long run. Additionally, examination malpractice has become the order of the day. Unserious students bribe the lecturers to earn high scores after examinations, while the scores of those who studied intensely are reduced (Okoye et al., 2022). In addition, most of the available jobs in Nigeria are offered on the basis of nepotism and favoritism. Those prepared for the jobs are not offered the jobs, while those who lack the skills but know some top people at the organization are offered the jobs. Some of the lazy students

also engage in some social vices like ‘yahoo yahoo’ and the recent one called ‘yahoo plus; to make quick money, while those serious ones are not adequately compensated. Consequently, most discourages serious and hard working students are discouraged and sometimes tow the part of laziness and indolent. As a result, the standard of education is greatly affected.

No definite plans after the compulsory one-year service: Most graduates who participate in the one-year mandatory NYSC programme often finish without any concrete plans for their future career. The NYSC programme ought to be an avenue for self-discovery and a period to acquire relevant skills for job markets. Some of them are expected to enroll in some skills acquisition in order to equip themselves practically and go into entrepreneurship since it is obvious that the available jobs cannot go round. They also know that after the programme, they are left to cater for themselves as there are no arrangements by the government to automatically absolve them into the labour market afterwards. But the reality is that most of them see that as an avenue to spend one year doing almost nothing but receiving stipends at the end of each month (Oloni et al., 2023).

Employers are more interested in how much they can gain from their employees: Most employers are not ready to get their employees trained from time to time in order to acquire skills that would enable their employees to perform their jobs better. They are not ready to spend money on ‘someone that would leave at the end of the day’ as some of them put it. However, they are more than willing to use their employees until the last sweat dries off their bodies. Interestingly, a typical Nigerian graduate must have changed their job at least thrice in a year. The reason for such action is usually tied to low or discouraging pay from employers (Okoye et al., 2022).

Lack of skillful knowledge: In Nigeria, most graduates feel it is degrading to learn a skill or take up a skill-oriented job simply because ‘they are graduates’. It is a truism that Nigerian society needs both skilled and semi-skilled professionals because they both contribute to the country’s GDP. In most countries across the world, possessing a skill or trade before graduation is compulsory. This is because it would enable them to have something to fall back to in case the anticipated job is not forthcoming. But such is not encouraged in Nigeria (Nwoke et al., 2022).

Corruption on the part of Nigerian leaders: Today, Nigerian leaders are not putting in their best in ensuring availability and provision of jobs for graduates. In fact, most people join politics purposely to enrich their pockets and possibly acquire illicit wealth for their immediate families. This explains the reason why most Nigerian leaders perform below expected standards at the national, state, and local levels. Hence, there is no dedicated leaders to monitor and regulate the quality and standard of education being offered in the classroom. Also, the national resources that are supposed to be used for the common good of all is embezzled by some

privileged individuals at the top and sent into their private accounts, leaving the masses to their fate (Okoye et al., 2022).

Possible Solutions to the Problem of Unemployability among Nigerian Graduates

Some of the possible solutions to the problem of unemployability among Nigerian graduates as suggested by Oladipo et al. (2023) are highlighted and explained as follows:

Educational Reform: The need for curriculum overhaul is widely recognized. A 2023 study by Oladipo et al. found that 68% of Nigerian employers believed university curricula were not adequately preparing graduates for the workforce. The World Economic Forum's "Future of Jobs Report 2023" emphasized the importance of integrating digital skills across all disciplines. In response, the National Universities Commission (NUC) launched the "Core Curriculum and Minimum Academic Standards" (CCMAS) in 2022, aiming to make Nigerian university education more responsive to 21st-century needs. For instance, majority of University across Nigeria have introduced a compulsory entrepreneurship course for all students. The African Development Bank's "Coding for Employment" programme partnered with several Nigerian universities to introduce digital skills courses.

Skills Development Programmes: The World Bank's "Digital Economy for Africa" initiative, active in Nigeria since 2019, has supported various digital skills training programmes. According to their 2023 progress report, over 200,000 Nigerians have benefited from these programmes. The Lagos State Employment Trust Fund (LSETF) reported in their 2022 annual report that their skills acquisition programmes had trained over 50,000 youth, with a 60% employment rate post-training. For instance, the Federal Government's N-Power program, which provides skills training and temporary employment to youth, reported reaching 500,000 beneficiaries in its 2022 impact assessment.

Entrepreneurship Support: The Global Entrepreneurship Monitor's 2022/2023 report on Nigeria highlighted that access to finance remains a major constraint for young entrepreneurs. However, there have been some positive initiatives such as the Central Bank of Nigeria's Agri-Business/Small and Medium Enterprises Investment Scheme (AGSMEIS) disbursed ₦134.63 billion to 37,571 beneficiaries as of December 2022, according to the CBN's 2022 Annual Report. The Tony Elumelu Foundation Entrepreneurship Programme, which provides seed capital and mentorship to young African entrepreneurs, supported 1,000 Nigerian startups in 2022 alone, as per their annual report.

Industrial Policy: Nigeria's efforts to diversify its economy have shown some progress. The National Bureau of Statistics' "Nigerian Gross Domestic Product Report" (Q2 2023) indicated that the non-oil sector contributed 93.99% to the nation's GDP, growing by 2.41% in real terms. The Nigeria Industrial Revolution Plan (NIRP), launched in 2014 and still ongoing, aims to

increase manufacturing's contribution to GDP. The 2023 review by the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment reported some success in sectors like cement production and textile manufacturing.

Infrastructure Development: The "National Integrated Infrastructure Master Plan" (2020-2043) outlines ambitious goals for infrastructure development. The 2023 progress report by the National Planning Commission indicated that while challenges remain, there have been notable improvements in road and rail infrastructure. The Rural Electrification Agency's (REA) 2022 annual report stated that their Nigeria Electrification Project (NEP) had provided electricity to over 5 million Nigerians through off-grid solutions.

Labour Market Information Systems: The National Bureau of Statistics has been working on improving labor market information. Their "Labour Force Statistics: Unemployment and Underemployment Report" (Q4 2020, the most recent as of my last update) provided detailed data on employment trends. The Federal Ministry of Labour and Employment launched the National Electronic Labour Exchange (NELEX) to match job seekers with employers. As of 2022, over 15,000 employers and 200,000 job seekers were registered on the platform. For instance, the Nigeria Employers' Consultative Association (NECA) conducts regular skills gap analyses in various sectors. Likewise, the National Universities Commission (NUC) initiated a Graduate Tracking System in 2022 to monitor the employment outcomes of university graduates.

This is suffice to say that while challenges persist, there are concerted efforts across various sectors to address the issue of graduate unemployability in Nigeria. The key lies in sustaining and scaling up these initiatives, ensuring they reach a significant portion of the population, and continually adapting them to meet evolving market needs.

Acquiring Employability and Marketability Skills: Strategies to Reducing Unemployment Among Nigerian Graduates

The high rate of unemployment among graduates in Nigeria and many other countries has led to increased focus on employability and marketability skills as crucial strategies to bridge the gap between education and employment. These skills go beyond academic qualifications and are essential for graduates to secure and maintain employment in an increasingly competitive job market.

Defining Employability and Marketability Skills

Employability skills are the attributes, capacities, and knowledge that make an individual more likely to gain and succeed in employment (Sumanasiri et al., 2015). Marketability skills, on the other hand, refer to the ability to effectively market oneself to potential employers (Finch et al., 2013).

A recent study by the World Economic Forum (2023) identified the top skills for the future workforce, including:

Analytical thinking and innovation; Active learning and learning strategies; Complex problem-solving; Critical thinking and analysis; Creativity, originality, and initiative; Leadership and social influence; Technology use, monitoring, and control; Technology design and programming; Resilience, stress tolerance, and flexibility; Reasoning, problem-solving, and ideation; Importance of Employability and Marketability Skills

Meanwhile, research has consistently shown the importance of these skills in reducing graduate unemployment. For instance, a study by Pitan (2016) found that Nigerian graduates with high employability skills were 2.5 times more likely to secure employment within six months of graduation compared to those with low employability skills. Likewise, the Nigeria Employers' Consultative Association (NECA) report (2022) highlighted that 80% of employers consider employability skills as important as or more important than technical skills when hiring graduates.

Furthermore, other strategies to enhance employability and marketability skills are highlighted and discussed below;

a. Curriculum Integration:

Universities should integrate employability skills into their curricula. The National Universities Commission's Core Curriculum and Minimum Academic Standards (CCMAS) initiative in 2022 is a step in this direction, aiming to make Nigerian university education more responsive to industrial needs.

b. Industrial Partnerships:

Collaborations between universities and industries can provide students with real-world experience. The Lagos State University's partnership with PwC Nigeria in 2023 to offer internships and mentorship programs is an example of such initiatives (Lagos State University, 2023).

c. Soft Skills Training:

Dedicated programmes focusing on communication, teamwork, and leadership can enhance graduates' employability. The British Council's "Employability Skills for Graduates" programme in Nigeria has trained over 5,000 graduates since its inception in 2020 (British Council Nigeria, 2023).

d. Digital Skills Development:

With the increasing digitalization of the workplace, digital skills are crucial. The World Bank's Digital Economy for Africa (DE4A) initiative has supported various digital skills training programmes in Nigeria, benefiting over 200,000 individuals as of 2023 (World Bank, 2023).

e. Entrepreneurship Education:

Encouraging entrepreneurial mindsets can create job creators rather than just job seekers. The Tony Elumelu Foundation Entrepreneurship Programme supported 1,000 Nigerian startups in 2022 alone (Tony Elumelu Foundation, 2023).

f. Career Counseling and Guidance:

Providing students with information about career paths and job market trends can help them make informed decisions. The National Career Development Association (NCDA) Nigeria chapter has been working to promote career counseling in Nigerian institutions (NCDA Nigeria, 2022).

g. Personal Branding and CV Writing:

Teaching students how to effectively market themselves is crucial. LinkedIn's "Rock Your Profile" workshops, conducted in partnership with Nigerian universities in 2022, reached over 10,000 students (LinkedIn, 2023).

Challenges to Implementation of Employability Policy Programmes in Nigeria

While progress is being made, challenges remain and among which are as follows:

Resource Constraints: Many institutions lack the resources to implement comprehensive employability programs.

Scalability: Ensuring these initiatives reach a significant portion of the graduate population is a challenge.

Rapidly Changing Job Market: Skills in demand are constantly evolving, requiring continuous updates to training programs.

In essence, enhancing employability and marketability skills is a crucial strategy in addressing graduate unemployment. It requires a concerted effort from educational institutions, industries, government, and students themselves. By focusing on these skills, graduates can become more competitive in the job market, potentially reducing unemployment rates and contributing to economic growth. As the World Economic Forum's "Future of Jobs Report 2023" emphasizes,

the ability to adapt and acquire new skills will be crucial in the rapidly evolving job market. Therefore, strategies to enhance employability and marketability skills should be dynamic, continuously evolving to meet the changing demands of the global economy.

Empirical Review

Owolabi and Adeosun (2023), in their own study examined graduate unemployment in Nigeria by Interrogating into the survival strategies of Lagos Youths. The study utilised a cross-sectional research design and a descriptive survey. Mixed research method was used (quantitative & qualitative research methods). The population of the study comprised of youths who resided in Lagos with no jobs and have graduated for at least one year. Using a non-probability sampling technique, purposive sampling technique was adopted to select the study location, while snowball sampling technique was utilised to select 450 respondents who participated in the quantitative study and 15 respondents for the qualitative study. Findings revealed that these unemployed graduates are involved in both legitimate and illegitimate means to survive; however, these illegitimate means are detrimental to the economic sustainability of Nigeria. The study therefore recommends that attention be paid to both the manufacturing and industrial sectors in order to bring back these misplaced jobs.

Aminu (2019) on the other hand examined characterising graduate unemployment in Nigeria as education-job mismatch problem. Variance of relative unemployment and proportional index of unemployed and employed were used to explain the mismatch from 2012 to 2016. Mismatch was found to be low but increasing in the entire labour market.

Aggregate unemployment rate was structurally dependent on unemployment rates among those without education and those who had secondary education while the rate was cyclically affected by unemployment rates in the ranks of those who had post-secondary education (graduates) and those who underwent less than primary education. The results of the proportional index analysis showed that the graduates of Medical Sciences, Social Sciences/Business Studies and Engineering would not experience unemployment, while graduates with specialisations in Education, Law, Arts and Sciences were most likely to be unemployed in the Nigerian labour market. A number of reasons were offered to explain the plausibility of these results, while some solutions were put forward to address unemployment among graduates of the latter set of disciplines.

The study concluded that to address the problems of unemployment across disciplines, there is a need to implement programme specific to each discipline. For instance, lawyers may have to be equipped with other disciplines in high demand while undergoing training in their respective universities. Lawyers-in-training or those of them who are unemployed can be encouraged to get certificated in business-related disciplines to bolster their employability.

Nwankwo and Ifejiofor (2014) investigated the impact of unemployment on Nigerian economic development in some selected local government area of Anambra State, Nigeria to find out the causes of unemployment in Nigeria and how it has impeded the economic development. These and others form the researcher's reason for this study. Descriptive research design was adopted. The population includes all the unemployed youth from the three selected Local Government Council (Oyi, Idemili North and South) which its figure is estimated to be about 2.3 million youth (NPC, 2006). 30 youths were drawn from each of the Local Government Council. Convenience sampling technique was applied. Both primary and secondary data source was used. Pearson correlation test was used for the test of hypotheses. The results of the test hypotheses revealed that unemployment impedes the economic growth and development of Nigeria. Government programmes have in many ways helped in tackling the problems of unemployment in Nigeria. There are possible ways that could be put forward in ensuring the reduction of unemployment level in Nigeria. Furthermore, the study recommended that the federal government should hasten the power sector reforms and re-stabilize the power sector to end the looming energy crisis in Nigeria

Theoretical Framework: Adaptation of Anomie/Strain Theory

Adaptation in Anomie/Strain theory was propounded by Robert Merton (1938) and this informs the main trust of this theoretical paper. This theory was informed by Durkheim's writing on anomie and argued that anomie does not result simply from unregulated goals, but rather, from a faulty relationship between cultural goals and the legitimated means to access them. While we are all socialized to desire success, we do not all have the same opportunities to become successful (Wajim, 2020). Thus, Merton defined several adaptations to anomie and strain. He argued that there are five general adaptations to anomie (Merton, 1938). The key to each is whether there is an acceptance or rejection of the cultural goals of success, and whether or not the choice is to strive for the goal via legitimate or conforming means. Hence, he identified conformity, innovation, ritualism, retreatism and rebellion as the modes of adaptation when the goals are to be achieved.

Conformity: is the most common adaptation (Deflem, 2018). Conformists have accepted the cultural goal of success or wealth attainment, and they are trying to achieve it via legitimate means. Most college students might be considered conformists as they work hard to earn degrees to get better jobs and have more success after graduation. For Merton, conformity was only the non-deviant adaptation to strain and anomie.

Innovation: is the adaptation for those who have accepted the cultural goal of success/wealth attainment but are trying to achieve it via illegitimate means. Any crime for profit would be an example of innovation (Okorie & Raphael, 2018). Robbers, thieves. Drug dealers and high priced call girls among others would be classified as innovators on Merton's adaptations.

Ritualism: This is the category for those who have abandoned the cultural goals of success/wealth attainment but continue to use legitimate means to make their living (Wajim, 2020). The dedicated workers who will never advance to management might be considered ritualists in Merton's typology (Owolabi & Adeosun, 2023).

Retreatism: This is the adaptation of those who have rejected the cultural goal of success/wealth attainment and have also rejected the legitimate means. The chronically homeless and serious drug addicts according to Shimfe and Wajim (2020) might be considered retreatists in this model.

Rebellion: This is the category for political deviants (Price, 2015); those who don't play by the rules but work to change the system to their own liking. Rebels reject the cultural goal of success/wealth attainment and replace it with another primary goal; they may use either legitimate or illegitimate means to achieve this goal. The clearest example of rebellion would be terrorist groups, who often use violence in an attempt to achieve political goals (Okorie & Raphael, 2018).

The strength of this theory in the paper lies in its analysis of coping behaviour in a situation of unemployment, with the reflection on the theory of anomie and adaptation mechanisms, allowing better understanding of various reactions to the particular situation of strain. Unemployment is an individual experience and youths are faced with the problems of survival, this informs the strategies they adopt utilizing any approach put forward by Merton, whether legitimate or otherwise. This was in consistency with (Moffitt, 2014; Deflem, 2018) where it was documented that unemployment brings strain between expectations and the lack of opportunities for success. This encourages people especially the underprivileged to engage in stealing, drugs and other illegitimate activities to achieve their goals.

Discussions

This paper attempted to review the nexus between unemployment and unemployability in the Nigerian labour market space. The paper revealed from the reports of the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024) that Nigeria's unemployment rate stood at 33.3% in the fourth quarter of 2020, marking a significant increase from 27.1% in the second quarter of the same year, and increased to 37.4 percent in the last quarter of 2022 and currently increasing from 4.2 to 5 percent in the third quarter of 2023. This translates to approximately 23.2 million currently unemployed Nigerians, a figure that underscores the severity of the situation. This means that youth unemployment rate is particularly alarming and seems to be unabated with 42.5% of young people aged 15-34 being currently unemployed.

The paper also identified some of the reasons in line with the submissions of Nwoke et al., (2022), Okoye et al., (2022), Oloni et al., (2023) and Arirahu (2022) among others why Nigerian

graduates are unemployed even while in the labour market includes but not limited to lack of employability skills, lack of emphasis laid on entrepreneurship in the school curriculum, the quality of training not in sync with the situation of the society, lecturers not possessing current knowledge, endemic corruption among leaders and even employers, students apathetic to education and lack of viable plans after NYSC are all contributing factors to the seemingly high rate of unemployment and underemployment in the country. Addressing this challenge will require a multi-faceted approach that encompasses economic diversification, skills development, and targeted interventions to support vulnerable groups and regions.

The paper likewise revealed in line with the submissions of Oladipo et al., (2023) among others some of the major solutions to the problem of unemployability in Nigeria to include but not limited to overhauling educational reforms, organizing marketability and employability skills acquisition program, establishing labour market information system, infrastructural development, viable industrial policy formulation, entrepreneurial supports among others. This is suffice to say that while challenges persist, there are concerted efforts across various sectors to address the issue of graduate unemployability in Nigeria. The key lies in sustaining and scaling up these initiatives, ensuring they reach a significant portion of the population, and continually adapting them to meet evolving market needs.

Conclusions

The relationship between unemployment and unemployability among Nigerian graduates is complex, multifaceted, and deeply rooted in the country's socio-economic fabric. This nexus represents a critical challenge that has significant implications for Nigeria's development trajectory and the well-being of its youth population. At its core, this issue reflects a fundamental mismatch between the skills and knowledge imparted by the Nigerian education system and the evolving demands of the labour market. The high rate of unemployment among graduates is not merely a result of a lack of job opportunities, but also stems from the inability of many graduates to meet the specific skill requirements of available positions. This unemployability factor exacerbates the unemployment situation, creating a vicious cycle that is difficult to break.

Many Nigerian universities continue to use curricula that have not been substantially updated to reflect current industry needs. This results in graduates who are well-versed in theory but lack practical, industry-relevant skills. The National Universities Commission's efforts to implement the Core Curriculum and Minimum Academic Standards (CCMAS) in 2022 represent a step towards addressing this issue, but the impact is yet to be fully realized. The lack of meaningful internship and industrial attachment opportunities during university education leaves many graduates without the practical experience employers seek. This gap between academic knowledge and practical application contributes significantly to unemployability.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from the extensive review and analysis of the unemployment and unemployability situation in Nigeria, here are some recommendations to address these interconnected issues:

- i. **Holistic Educational Reform and Skills Development:** Employers often cite lack of soft skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and effective communication as reasons for not hiring most graduates in Nigeria. This deficit points to a need for a more holistic approach to education that goes beyond academic knowledge. There should be an implementation of a nationwide educational reform program that aligns curricula with industrial needs and integrates practical, digital, and soft skills training across all levels of education.
- ii. **Public-Private Partnership for Job Creation and Skill Matching:** The federal and state governments should establish a robust public-private partnership framework to stimulate job creation, improve skill matching, and enhance graduate employability in the country.
- iii. **Entrepreneurship Ecosystem Development and Support:** There should be development of a comprehensive entrepreneurship ecosystem to encourage self-employment and job creation among graduates. Furthermore, collaboration between government agencies, educational institutions, private sector entities, and international partners are crucial in the regular assessment and adaptation of entrepreneurial initiatives to ensure effectiveness in addressing the dynamic challenges of unemployment and unemployability among Nigerian graduates.

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